

The Fiction

It is the year 2030. Ada is a maintainer of an open-source software hosted on GitHub called FutureX. Since FutureX receives thousands of monthly contributions, she spends considerable time maintaining issues and reviewing contributions. To reduce the effort she spends on repetitive tasks and help her be more productive, Ada relies on more than ten software bots to help her. For example, one bot updates the project's dependencies to the latest version when they become available, another bot makes contributors aware of code coverage, and another bot closes pull requests that have been inactive (stale) for a long time.

Ada recognizes that these bots reduce her burden with repetitive tasks and speed up the pull request review. However, she noticed that the other maintainers of FutureX complain about bot annoying behavior.

"You are talking to the person who submitted the pull request and then a bot comes in and adds information in the middle of your conversation," said Ellie.

John agreed. *"I agree with Ellie... Sometimes the bot comments are really verbose and overuse visual elements."*

"I feel the same," said Anne agreeing with both Ellie and John, *"these bots work a lot and generate so many notifications for me to check."*

After discussing with other project members, Ada concluded that the most recurrent problem is the introduction of noise into developers' communication channels.

"The noise leads to an overload of information, which negatively impacts our communication and the development workflow," complemented Ada.

Ada and her team started to discuss the idea of developing a Meta-bot to mitigate the noise caused by the existing bots. The Meta-bot would orchestrate and mediate the action of other bots used on pull requests. You heard about this Meta-bot and decided to help Ada's team to design it.